

Use of Plastic Waste in Flexible Pavements: A Review

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Abstract:

Plastic has become a constant element in our lives. It's everywhere: product packaging, cosmetic ingredients, textiles, mobile phones, etc. It's even in the chewing gum you might be chewing on right now! Its omnipresence is such that many would find the mere fact of giving it up a difficult task. Reducing the consumption of plastics therefore requires not only a change in habits, but also a change of mindset. Safe disposal of waste plastic is a serious environmental problem. In this paper the authors have listed the use of plastic in flexible pavements and brief overview of abrasive flow machining process is done.

1. INTRODUCTION

Plastic has become a constant element in our lives. It's everywhere: product packaging, cosmetic ingredients, textiles, mobile phones, etc. It's even in the chewing gum you might be chewing on right now! Its omnipresence is such that many would find the mere fact of giving it up a difficult task. Reducing the consumption of plastics therefore requires not only a change in habits, but also a change of mindset. Safe disposal of waste plastic is a serious environmental problem. Being a non-biodegradable material, it does not decay over time and even if dumped in landfills, finds its way back in the environment through air and water erosion, can choke the drains and drainage channels, can be eaten by unsuspecting grazing animals causing them illness and death, can contaminate the construction fill etc. The best way of disposal of waste plastic is its recycling to the maximum extent and many developed countries have recycled waste plastic to manufacture various products, including some used in heavy construction e.g., Railway sleepers.

Plastic trash pollution pollutes not only the land but also the water environment. The world's oceans contain around 150 tonnes of plastic trash [1]. Plastic Man of India solved the plastic waste problem by constructing a plastic tar road, which is still in use today [2]. Since then, technology has progressed significantly. The Indian Roads Congress and the Central Pollution Control Board both employ the same strategy [3].

In India, the rate of waste plastic manufacturing is exceptionally high, and there are several dumping yards in every state and district where waste plastic is deposited, resulting in significant pollution, mosquito breeding, and other issues. It not only contributes to pollution, but it also has an impact on life on the earth. Malaria, respiratory issues, and a weakened immune system are just a few of the ailments brought on by the dumping of waste plastic. Since the last two decades, waste plastic has been employed in bituminous pavements, and 10% of it has proven to be environmentally beneficial and cost-effective. It reduces the volume of air voids, shrinkage, and maintenance costs. Increases the bond

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128

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strength between aggregates and bitumen and provide a pavement that stands with heavy traffic; percentage cost reduction for one cum material mix is 5.18% [4-10]. The pavements made using waste plastic are durable compared to conventional flexible pavements [11]. It can resist higher temperatures and loads when utilised in road construction. Plastics that have been coated reduce porosity, moisture absorption and increase soundness. Because the polymer-coated aggregate bitumen mix has a greater Marshall Stability value and a sufficient Marshall Coefficient, it is a preferable material for flexible pavement construction [12]. Plastic addition is an innovative method that strengthens road construction while also extending its life [13]. This proves that coating the aggregate with a polymer has numerous benefits and, as a result, aids in increasing the flexible pavement quality, not only for the pavement but also for the aggregate [14]. The addition of plastic garbage to the bitumen enhanced the softening point—the softening point increases as the percentage of plastic garbage increases. Plastic addition is a novel approach for strengthening and prolonging the life of road construction. Demonstrates that coating aggregate with a polymer offers a number of advantages and, as a result, contributes to improving the flexible pavement quality, not only for the pavement but also for the aggregate [15]. The softening point of the bitumen was improved by adding plastic rubbish to it. As the percentage of plastic rubbish added increases, the softening point rises. The softening point may be affected by the chemical composition of the polymers used.

In view of the above, this study attempts to review research on use of plastic waste in flexible pavements. India has a population of more than 1.4 billion and generates 26,000 tonnes of plastic waste – every day. Currently, a large fraction of plastic waste in India goes to landfill or leaks into the environment, mismanaged waste in India in 2023 was very huge 7,300,752 tonnes of plastic. Therefore, it is the need of the hour to utilise this waste material in construction. Flexible pavement construction is one potential area where this can be used.

Over the years many papers have been published on the topic of plastic waste addition in flexible pavement and road construction. Most published papers are research articles that deal with different plastic products like polypropylene (PP), polyvinylchloride (PVC), polyethylene (PE), etc. from waste as a modifier and use different modifications techniques like wet process, a dry process, or some modified process. Hence, there is a need for a review paper that discusses and compacts the results and processing techniques used in the existing literature.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Manju, R. & Sheema, K. [16] concluded that the utilization of plastic waste in bituminous mixes enhances its properties and also its strength. This will not only strengthen the pavement and also increases its durability. The polymer coated on aggregates reduces the voids and moisture absorption. This results in the reduction of ruts and there is no pothole formation. The plastic pavement can withstand heavy traffic and are durable than flexible pavement. The use of plastic mix will reduce the bitumen content by 10% and increases the strength and performance of the road.

Dr. R. Vasudevan [17-18] stated that use of waste plastic in bitumen increase the binding property as compared to the conventional bitumen. It improves the properties of bitumen resulting in increase in Softening Point and decrease in Penetration value thus improving the durability.

Shafiq, H. & Hamid, A. [19] stated that plastic waste should be reused to eliminate the threat to the surroundings. One such reuse can be in the construction of flexible pavements. Plastic coated aggregates have proved to offer better resistance to abrasion and wear and tear. Moreover, the bond between these plastic-coated aggregates and the bitumen is also very strong due to increased contact area between plastic (polymers) and bitumen. Such roads show better performance and have increased life spans.

Basuki, R., Khoiri, M. & Firdausi [20] investigated the effects of the Polyethylene terephthalate (PET) on Marshall parameters on asphalt concrete pavement. PET belongs to the family of polyesters. It has a semi-crystalline form when stable. It is recyclable and shows resistance to impact, moisture, alcohols, and solvents. It is among those plastics which are an important part of your everyday life. The wet method is used in this research. In this research, asphalt with penetration of 60/70 is used. Its optimum asphalt content (OAC) is 5.7 percent while the percentages of the added PET are 3 percent, 4 percent, 5 percent, 6 percent, and 7 percent of the asphalt by weight. The results show that the addition of PET plastic waste into the mixture has a significant positive effect on the Marshall parameters of asphalt concrete pavement. The addition of PET waste has been able to increase the value of other Marshall parameters, including Voids in Mix (VIM), Voids in Mineral Aggregates (VMA), Voids Filled with Asphalt (VFA), Flow, and Marshall Quotient (MQ).

Ali R. Khaloo, M. Dehestani & P. Rahmatabadi [21] investigated the feasibility of using elastic and flexible tire–rubber particles as aggregate in concrete. Tire–rubber particles composed of tire chips, crumb rubber, and a combination of tire chips and crumb rubber, were used to replace mineral aggregates in concrete. These particles were used to replace 12.5%, 25%, 37.5%, and 50% of the total mineral aggregate's volume in concrete. Cylindrical shape concrete specimens 15 cm in diameter and 30 cm in height were fabricated and cured. The fresh rubberized concrete exhibited lower unit weight and acceptable workability compared to plain concrete. The results of a uniaxial compressive strain control test conducted on hardened concrete specimens indicate large reductions in the strength and tangential modulus of elasticity. A significant decrease in the brittle behaviour of concrete with increasing rubber content is also demonstrated using nonlinearity indices. The maximum toughness index, indicating the post failure strength of concrete, occurs in concretes with 25% rubber content. Unlike plain concrete, the failure state in rubberized concrete occurs gently and uniformly, and does not cause any separation in the specimen. Crack width and its propagation velocity in rubberized concrete are lower than those of plain concrete. Ultrasonic analysis reveals large reductions in the ultrasonic modulus and high sound absorption for tire–rubber concrete.

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130

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Shaikh, A., Khan, N. & Kale, G. [22] studied that Plastic was found to be an effective binder for bitumen mixes used in flexible pavements. This efficient method helps the pavements to resist higher temperature by minimizing the formation of cracks and reducing rainwater infiltration which otherwise leads to the development of potholes. These pavements have shown improved crushing and abrasion values and reduced water seepage. Plastic roads would be a boon for India's hot and extremely humid climate, where temperatures frequently cross 50°C and torrential rains create havoc, leaving most of the roads with big potholes. Moreover, the steady increment in high traffic intensity in terms of commercial vehicles, and the significant variation in daily and seasonal temperature put us in a demanding situation to think of some alternatives for the improvisation of the pavement characteristics and quality by applying some necessary modifications which shall satisfy both the strength as well as economic aspects. Also considering the environmental approach, due to excessive use of polythene in the day to day business, the pollution to the environment is enormous. Since the polythenes are not biodegradable, the need of the current hour is to use the waste polyethene in some beneficial purposes.

X. Xu, Z. Leng, J. Lan et al. [23] studied the feasibility of collectively recycling the two types of waste into performance-increasing modifiers for asphalt pavements was analyzed. This study aimed to investigate the recycling mechanisms of waste PET-derived additives under the treatment of two amines, triethylenetetramine (TETA) and ethanolamine (EA), and characterize the performances of these additives in modifying rubberized bitumen, a bitumen modified by waste tyre rubber. To this end, infrared spectroscopy and thermal analyses were carried out on the two PET-derived additives (PET-TETA and PET-EA). In addition, infrared spectroscopy, viscosity, dynamic shear rheology, and multiple stress creep recovery tests were performed on the rubberized bitumen samples modified by the two PET-derived additives. They concluded that waste PET can be chemically up cycled into functional additives, which can increase the overall performance of the rubberized bitumen. The recycling method developed in this study not only helps alleviate the landfilling problems of both waste PET plastic and scrap tyres, but also turns these wastes into value-added new materials for building durable pavements.

J. Santos et al. [24] studied– from an environmental perspective – the processes that lead to the conversion of waste plastics into recycled plastic pellets to be used either as an additive (wet method) or as a replacement of natural aggregate (dry method) in the production of asphalt mixes. Analyses were conducted by considering several replacement ratios of virgin material by its recycled counterpart in the so-called wet and dry method. A case study considering the production of recycled-plastic asphalt to be applied in the construction of a typical surface layer of a road in Victoria was evaluated. In general, the results show that recycling plastics as a polymer for bitumen modification and as a synthetic aggregate replacement in asphalt mixes has the potential to be environmentally advantageous compared to their virgin counterpart (i.e., virgin polymers and natural quarry aggregates).

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131

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Even if the total amount of recycled plastics is a small percentage of the total asphalt mix, the wet method has proven to be environmentally friendly (fewer emissions), cost effective (RPP is cheaper than virgin polymers) and efficient in improving bitumen performance. Specifically, a reduction of up to 10.2% of CO₂-eq emissions was observed when replacing 8% of virgin polyethylene with the same amount of RPP; the environmental benefit becomes even more evident (−15.6%) when replacing SBS with RPP. All the environmental indicators were generally improved by the use of RPP.

Yuetan Ma et al. uniquely used plastic in bituminous macadam (BM), they tried to resolve the compatibility problem of crumb rubber modified bitumen by using a composite of crumb rubber and plastic to modify the bitumen. They concluded that plastic improves the rutting resistance of bitumen while rubber improves the compatibility of the blend, but this type of modifier was not feasible for field implementation [25]. In the second study, they focused on one composition of composite i.e. plastic to rubber ratio was 1:2, unlike the first study and changed the ageing time to monitor its effect on the thermal stability of modified bitumen. They concluded that, composite modifier, at high and moderate temperatures show good fatigue resistance [26]. Implementation of composite modifier requires more data on Marshall test results of composite modified BM. A review on abrasive flow machining process for nano- surface finishing is done [31-50] in which flow of polymer media past the surface is done.

3. CONCLUSION

As discussed above, a good amount of work has been done on plastic waste. Various studies have been carried out to recycle and reuse it in Bituminous pavement construction [15, 16, 18, 30, 51]. Most previous studies have focused on the physical recycling of PET wastes as polymer modifiers or partial replacement of fine aggregates to improve the fatigue resistance, stiffness, rutting resistance, and strength of bitumen mixes [27–30]. However, the physical recycling of PET wastes in bitumen pavements is hindered by the limitations of potential pollutant emission at high construction temperatures and low storage stability of the PET-modified bitumen. Therefore, chemical recycling of waste PET in bitumen pavement may also be considered. An ammonolysis method has been designed to produce functionalized additives using waste PET. Chemical recycling of waste PET in bitumen pavement is not yet studied. So thorough research is needed on the properties and performances of the PET derived additives in Bituminous pavement.

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